

The implementation of integrated pest management (ipm) on rainfed rice in Gunungkidul Yogyakarta

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ABSTRACT

One of the problems of rainfed rice in Gunungkidul District is the disruption of pests and diseases. Farmer awareness and knowledge on integrated pest management is still low. Generally, chemical control is used dominantly by farmers. The aim of this research was to determine the effect of integrated pest management model on damage intensity of major pest and rainfed rice yield. This research was conducted in Wareng village, Wonosari sub-district, Gunungkidul district in January until April 2018. The research was carry out on 0.5 hectares area as IPM model and 0.5 hectares as control (conventional model/non-IPM). IPM model adopts the integrated crop management (ICM) concept and pest-disease control based on threshold of control. Sampling was done randomly on 5 plots and 25 hill per plot. Damage intensity of major pest and disease was recorded once every two weeks. The rainfed rice yield was measured by tile method on 2,5 m x 2,5 m areas with 9 replications. Results of the research showed that the IPM model reduced damage intensity of blast disease and rice bugs. Rainfed rice yield in IPM is significantly higher (6,82 ton/ha) compared to conventional model (5,5 kg ton/ha).

Keywords: IPM, pest and disease, rainfed rice

INTRODUCTION

Gunungkidul Regency is the major rice producer of rainfed rice in Yogyakarta. Rainfed rice production in Gunungkidul Regency has decreased in the last five years. Rainfed rice production in 2012 was 204.689 tons, while in 2016 production reached 168.249 tons only (Statistics of Yogyakarta, 2017). One of the problems encountered in the cultivation of rainfed rice in Gunungkidul District is the disruption of pests and diseases that always harming the farmers. The major pests of rainfed rice are rice whorl maggot, brown planthopper, stem borer, rice bug, mole cricket, and white grub (Baehaki and widiarta, 2008; Suharto and Usyati, 2008; Kartohardjono et al 2008). While the major diseases of rainfed rice are blast disease, bacterial leaf blight and tungro viruses (Santoso dan Nasution, 2008; Kadir et al, 2008, Muhsin dan Widiarta, 2008).

The level of pests attack in rainfed rice are light until heavy varies. Heavy damage can cause “puso” (harvest failure), which depends on the environmental factors of the local agro ecosystem, cultivation factors and farmer’s knowledge of rainfed rice pests and its control activities. Generally, chemical pesticide control is the dominant used by farmers. The use of chemical pesticides has a negative impact on the environment such as the instability of the ecosystem, the content of chemical residues in crops and their processed materials, environmental pollution and its poisoning even death in humans (Wahyuni, 2010; Yuantari, 2009). Chemical pesticides also cause a resurgence of brown planthopper on rice (Trisnaningsih, 2015).

Integrated Pest Management (IPM) is a model agriculture management that is recommended to control pests and diseases of rice. This concept is implemented by considering the ecosystem, stability, and sustainability of production in accordance with the demands of good agricultural practices. IPM aims to limit the use of chemical pesticides by introducing the concept of a control threshold as a basis for determining pest control (Effendi, 2009). IPM control include: (1) cultivation of healthy plants, (2) utilization of natural enemies, (3) planting resistant varieties, (4) mechanical control, (5) physical control, (6) genetic control, (7) Recommendation pesticides dose.

IPM model has been implemented in Indonesia since 1992 and strengthened by Laws of Republic Indonesia Number 12 of 1992 concerning Plant Cultivation Systems. However, farmers' knowledge about IPM is still not adequate. The aim of this research was to determine the effect of integrated pest management implementation on damage intensity of main pest-disease which affected and yield of rainfed rice..

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was conducted in Wareng village, Wonosari sub-district, Gunungkidul district from January to April 2018. The research was conducted on an area of 0.5 hectares as IPM implementation and 0,5 hectares as control (non IPM). IPM Implementation on rainfed rice in Gunungkidul also implemented the concept of integrated crop management by used superior variety (Inpari 10), good seed, optimal soil processing and balanced fertilization. Pest and disease control of rainfed rice is carried out based on the control threshold of each type of pest and disease. In addition prevention is carried out to maintain infection and the development of blast disease through environmental sanitation. Environmental sanitation is carried out by maintaining the cleanliness of the rice field environment of weeds which are alternative hosts and cleaning the remnants of plants infected with blast disease.

Sampling of pests and diseases was carried out using a randomized structured method by dividing the research fields into 5 observation blocks (as replications). Observations of pests and disease were carried out on 25 plant hills for each observation block. Observations were made on the level of severity of blast disease and rice stem borer population every 2 (two) weeks since the plant was 40 days after planting. Blast disease severity level is calculated using the following formula:

$$I = \frac{\sum(n.v)}{N.Z} \times 100\%$$

Explanation:

I = Blast disease severity level(%)

n = The number of infected leaves

v = Numerical value of symptom category

N = The total number of leaves observed

Scale of blast attack on rice leaves

Scale	Attack category	Status
1	1-5 % affected from leaf area	resistant
3	5-11 % affected from leaf area	Mild
5	>11 ≤ 25 % affected from leaf area	moderate
7	>25 - ≤ 75 % affected from leaf area	heavy
9	>75 - 100 % affected from leaf area	crop failure

Rice stem borer attack rates are calculated by the formula (Natawigena, 1989):

$$I = \frac{n}{N} \times 100\%$$

Explanation:

I = percentage of stem borer infestation(%)

n = number of damage tillers

N = total number of tiller

Neck blast sampling is done by calculating the number of panicles damage and the total number of panicles per observation sample. The severity of neck blast damage was calculated by the number of panicles damage divided by the total panicle observed was multiplied by 100%. Observation of damage due to rice bug “walang sangit” damage is done by counting the number of rice grains damage divided by the total number of rice grains multiplied by 100%.

The yield of rainfed rice was measured by the tile method $2.5 \text{ m}^2 \times 2.5 \text{ m}^2$, each of which carried 9 replications. The collected data were analyzed by t test with 5% accuracy. Arthropod sampling was carried out using an insect net which was swung in 10 double swings. The catch of insects were identified in the laboratory based on the key to insect determination (Kalshoven, 1981).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Blast Diseases Severity Level

Blast disease is the main disease that mostly attacks rainfed rice in Gunungkidul. However, the level of blast severity fluctuates and is influenced by environmental factors, especially climate. The results showed that in the IPM treatment, the leaf blast severity decreased from the first observation in 40 days after planting (DAP) to the third observation (70 DAP) and increase in the fourth observation (85 DAP). The blast diseases severity on treatment ranged from 5.10% to 7.81% and was included in the category of light damage (Figure 1).

In the control treatment (farmer cultivation method) the intensity of blast diseases severity on the first observation (40 dat) was included in the moderate category (22, 47%). However, blast damage tend to decrease until the fourth observation (85 dap) which ranges from 7.03% to 10.45% higher than the IPM treatment. Decreasing of leaf blast damage can be explained that the symptoms of blast damage do not develop actually, but because of the development of the growth of rice plants (the number of leaves and hills). The calculating the intensity of blast damage is effected by the number of leaves increasing caused leaves growth (N). Moreover, the decrease in the intensity of blast damage caused by effective use of pesticides based on Santosa and Nasution (2008) recommendations, namely at the time of primordia stadia and flowering stadia 5%.

The development of plant diseases is influenced by several factors, namely the pathogen, the environment and the plant itself (Semangun, 1996). The increase in intensity of leaf blast damage in the last observation (85 dap) was allegedly due to environmental factors that support the development of blast. Environmental factors that can support the development of diseases include weather (temperature and humidity). Rainfall that was still quite high at the end of observation caused the development of blast disease to increase again.

Based on observations at the beginning of planting, symptoms of blast disease were seen in weeds of animal feed plants (king grass) grown on field dike. This condition is available for blast inoculum and the area is endemic to blast disease. The severity of leaf blast damage on king grass plants reaches an

average of 33.91%. To prevent widespread blast diseases, sanitation of king grass was carried out (harvesting / cleaning) in IPM treatment. Environmental sanitation is a preventive step while supporting the concept of IPM and GAP

Figure 1. The intensity of blast disease attacks on IPM treatment and farmers' cultivation methods (control)

The results of (t test) statistical analysis showed that there were significant differences in the leaf blast and neck blast severity level throughout the observations of the IPM and the farmers cultivated (control) treatment (Table 1). The highest severity of leaf blast on IPM treatment was 10,32% and control was 22,47%. Likewise, the severity level of neck blast disease on IPM treatment was 7.11% an average and control was 16.45%. Neck blast occurred because of the inoculum of blast disease that infected the plant at the time of panicle formation.

Table 1. The disease severity level (%) of leaves blast and neck blast

Block	The Severity Level of Leaves Blast (%)				Neck Blast (%)
	40 dap	55 dap	70 dap	85 dap	
IPM	10.32 a	6.42a	5.10a	7.27a	7.11a
Control	22.47 b	7.03b	7.61b	10.47b	16.45b

Note: the numbers that are accompanied by the same letter in the column indicate that they are not significantly different at the level of the t-test with 5% accuracy. dap = day after planting

The intensity of rice stem borer damage

The percentage of rice stem borer infestation is classified as light damage category both in IPM and control treatments. At the beginning of observation (40 days), the percentage of rice stem borer infestation at PHT was low (0,67%). However, the intensity of the stem borer damage increased in the second and third observations, and decreased again in the fourth observation. Otherwise, the intensity of rice stem borer damage on the control treatment at the age of 40 DAP was 1.53%, the intensity of stem borer damage dropped in the second and third observations, and rose again in the fourth observation (Figure 2). The intensity of stem borer damage was still low and was under the threshold of control set by the Directorate General of Crop Protection namely 6% (vegetative stadia) and 10% (generative stadia). Therefore, the control of rice stem borer with insecticides are not carried out. In addition, it was also reported by Ratih et al (2014) that the application of IPM systems has not given a significant influence on rice stem borer populations and the intensity of damage.

Figure 2. The severity of blast disease damage on IPM and farmers' cultivation (control)treatment

The intensity of rice bug (*Leptocorisa oratorius*)

The results of the observation showed that the intensity of the rice bug damage on the IPM treatment was lower than the control (Figure 3). The results of the t test statistical analyses showed that there was a significant influence on the intensity of the rice bug damage on both treatments. The mean intensity of

rice bug damage on the IPM treatment $9.52\% \pm 0.94$ and control treatment $20.61\% \pm 1.94$. Symptoms of rice bug damage namely empty grain and incomplete filling. The rice fruit liquid is crushed and sucked by the rice bug when the grain filling process (Pracaya, 2007). The high damage of rice bug on the control is caused by the appearance of panicle rice was not in unison or early flowering so it became the target of a pest attack. While on the IPM treatment, flowering was more simultaneously.

Figure 3. The intensity of rice bug damage on IPM and farmers' cultivation (control) treatment

The population of arthropod

The observations on the number and type of insects found in rainfed rice crops in the vegetative and generative phases can be seen in Table 2. The results showed that the number of arthropods caught in the IPM treatment was higher than in the control both in the vegetative and generative phases. The catch of arthropods in the vegetative phase in the IPM treatment were 9 orders consisting of 16 families with total population was 146, of which 6 families had a role as pests and 10 families acted as natural enemies. While, the catch of arthropods in the generative phase in the IPM treatment were 9 orders consisting of 21 families with total population was 186, of which 9 families had a role as pests and 12 families acted as natural enemies.

The number and type of arthropod insects both as pest and natural enemies in the treatment of IPM were higher than in the control treatment. This

can be explained because in the IPM treatment use insecticides is very selective and limited, while in the treatment of control treatment use insecticides with a calendar system and is not in accordance with the recommendations both dose and frequency of application. Overuse pesticides can kill pests and natural enemies that are useful for the ecological balancing.

Table 2. The Population of Arthropod on IPM treatment and control (farmer's method)

No	The role of insect	Order	Family	Vegetative phases		Generative phases	
				IPM	Control	IPM	Control
1	Pest	Hemiptera	Alydidae/Leptocorisa	1	0	22	8
2		Homoptera	Delphacidae	18	7	26	22
3		Coleoptera	Crambidae	9	0	2	0
4		hemiptera	Flatidae	2	0	2	5
5		Lepidoptera	Noctuidae	1	0	1	0
6		Orthoptera	Grillidae	3	1	2	0
7		Lepidoptera	Pyralidae	0	0	2	1
8		Orthoptera	Acrididae	0	0	11	4
9		Hemiptera	Pentatomidae	0	0	20	4
		Amount		34	8	88	44
10	Natural enemy	Araneidae	Tetragnathidae	17	8	10	7
11		Hymenoptera	Braconidae	14	0	8	11
12		Diptera	Tachinidae	9	3	4	9
13		Hemiptera	Miridae	34	0	44	34
14		Hymenoptera	Elupidae/tetranagtidae	5	1	3	4
15		Coleoptera	Coccinellidae	2	0	5	3
16		Odonata	Coenagrionidae	11	0	7	1
17		Araneidae	Araenidae	1	0	0	0
18		Hymenoptera	Ichneumonidae	16	1	13	23
19		Orthoptera	Gryllotalpidae	3	0	2	0
20		Diptera	Dolichopodidae	0	0	1	0
21		Coleoptera	kumbang tanah	0	0	1	0
		Amount		112	13	98	92

Yield of rainfed rice

The rainfed rice harvest was measured by tile method. The results of statistical analysis of yield was significantly different between IPM treatment and control. The yield of IPM treatment was higher than control (Table 3). The yield of IPM treatment reached 6.47 t / ha and the farmer cultivation (control)

only reached 5.99 t / ha. The difference in yields is partly due to different levels of pest and disease damage, different ways of crops management. The high intensity of blast damage and rice bugs on control caused empty grain higher than IPM treatment.

Tabel 3. Yield on IPM treatment and farmer method (control)

Block	Yield (ton/ha dry grain harvest)
IPM	6,47 a
Control	5,99 b

Note: the numbers that are accompanied by the same letter in the column indicate that they are not significantly different at the level of the t-test with 5% accuracy

CONCLUSIONS

IPM treatment can decrease the intensity of blast and rice bug was s damage significantly than control (farmer cultivation system). It also had higher diversity of arthropod which acts as a pest or natural enemy. The IPM treatment in rainfed rice of Gunungkidul provides significantly higher yields (18%) compared to farmers cultivation system (control).

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